

ENHANCEMENT EFFICIENCY OF MICHELL-BANKI TURBINE USING NACA 6512 MODIFIED BLADE PROFILE VIA CFD

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Abstract

The small hydroelectric power plants (SHPP) are implemented in non-interconnected zones (NIZ) of developing countries. In which, the provision of electrical energy from the national interconnected system is not economically feasible. Therefore, in the literature, hydroelectric generation technologies have been implemented taking advantage of the energy available in the rivers. One of these technologies is the Michell-Banki type cross-flow turbines (MBT), which, despite having lower efficiencies than turbines such as Pelton and Francis, maintain their efficiency although fluctuations in site conditions. For this reason, different studies have been made to increase the efficiency of the MBT by making geometric modifications to both the nozzle and the rotor.

The purpose of this study is to determine numerically the effect of the geometry of the blades that form the runner on the efficiency of Michell-Banki Turbine (MBT). For this, two (2) geometries were studied corresponding to a circular sector of a standard tubular profile and an airfoil NACA 6512 modified in curvature profile and chord length, according to the profile of the standard tubular blade. For this study, transient simulations for multiphase water-air flow were implemented using a $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model in the Ansys 2020R1® CFX software. The two (2) turbine models were configured to the same hydraulic conditions of head and volumetric flow corresponding to 0.5 m and 16.27 L/s, respectively. Variations in rotational speed were configured between 100 and 200 RPM with 20 RPM steps. It was found that using the modified 6512 hydrodynamic profile, at 140 RPM increased efficiency by 6 %, compared to the conventional tubular type blade geometry.

Keywords: computational fluids dynamics, efficiency, cross-flow turbine, micro hydropower.

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1. Introduction

Due to the economic growth of the industry and the world population, increases in energy consumption are estimated between 40–45 % by 2050 [1] highlighting regions such as Asia where increases of up to 60 % are expected. Nowadays, hydroelectric energy constitutes about 61 % of the total world renewable energy, where small hydroelectric power plants (SHPP) contribute around 7 % [2]. However, for renewable energies an average annual growth of 2.3 % is expected between 2015 and 2040 [3]. Due to this and environmental damage, governments are being forced to create general incentives for the development of clean energy [4].

The decentralized generation of electrical energy is intended to satisfy the demand in non-interconnected zones (NIZ) for the national service, which due to the costs of generation, transmission and distribution makes the provision of the service economically unfeasible [5], which

is why currently generating plants based on fossil fuels are implemented, generating greenhouse gases (GHG) and contributing to global warming; also with high generation costs due to the current price of oil [6]. For this reason, the SHPP's are presented as an excellent alternative to the problem of coverage of electricity supply in the NIZ with water potential [4–6].

In the SHPP's it is found different types of turbines such as Francis, Pelton, Turgo, Kaplan and MBT, of which the MBT reports the least efficiency, highlighting that compared to other technologies, they have advantages such as simplicity in design, low cost manufacturing and little variation in efficiency against changes in flow conditions [7, 8]. Due to this, different studies have presented improvements in the design methodology for the dimensioning of the MBT, allowing to significantly increase its performance and implementation in the SHPP's, which can be achieved from changes both in operating conditions and geometric modifications of each of its components [9].

Different studies concerning the incidence of the nozzle geometry allow to validate the potential for improvement in this component. Recently, in 2018 an increase of 5.33 % was found when using a metaheuristic model to optimize the geometry of the nozzle guide valve, which was validated by CFD simulation [2]. In addition, the behavior of the nozzle without a guide valve has been analyzed by means of 2D computer simulations, it was possible to find a new formula for the design of the rear wall of the nozzle, showing increases in MBT efficiency of up to 18 % [10, 11]. In the same way, a 2D CFD analysis of the nozzle geometry and its effect on the MBT efficiency was performed, using a linear nozzle, which ensures an almost constant value of the angle of attack, reporting maximum efficiencies of 86 % [12].

Regarding the runner has been investigated by CFD analysis the incidence of the number of blades on the dynamic fluid behavior of the turbine, obtaining an efficiency of 73 % for a runner formed by 28 blades [13]. On the other hand, has been analyzed the effect of the blade position and the fluid angle of attack on the hydraulic performance of the MBT by means of 3D CFD analysis, finding the best hydraulic performance (88 %) for a 12° angle of attack [14]. In addition, have been evaluated the incidence angles of the fluid to the runner and the position of the blades using experimental tests, determining a maximum efficiency of 93 % for angles of attack of 8° [15]. Finally, a study analyzes the low efficiencies of MBTs using CFDs, caused by the interaction of the fluid with the rotor shaft, using a system that avoids the contact of the shaft with the cross flow, obtaining efficiencies above 58 % [16].

Finally, with respect to the profile of the blades and their incidence on the performance of the MBT, a study is carried out using CFD techniques analyzing the behavior of the rotor blades with and without edge, finding an improvement in the performance of the turbine when using blades with edge [17]. A new study is developed to verify the incidence of runner blade geometry on the efficiency of the MBT using the NACA 6712 and 6509 type hydrodynamic profiles, which have efficiencies of 47 % and 46 %, respectively [18]. The low efficiency found is mainly attributed to the difference in the radius of curvature of both profiles with respect to the conventional tubular type profile, affecting the dynamics of the fluid in the interaction region with the blades.

The potential improvement represented by the geometry profile of the blades that make up the runner in the efficiency of the MBT is evident. However, no enough studies were found by the authors that relate geometric parameters such as the radius of curvature, the radius of rounding both at the leading and trailing edge, and chord length, in the efficiency of the MBT. The purpose of this study is to determine numerically the effect of the geometry of the blades that form the rotor on the efficiency of a MBT, implementing NACA 6512 type blades modified in curvature in comparison to the standard tubular profile.

2. Methods

2.1. Research object

The MBT is a turbomachine that transforms the potential energy of the fluid into rotational kinetic energy, which is transformed into electrical current from a generator. The MBT is mainly made up of a nozzle, a runner and a housing as shown in **Fig. 1, a**. The fluid inlet through

the nozzle, which accelerates and directs the flow towards the runner, where the energy transfer between the fluid and the blades takes place during the first and second stage, transferring 75 and 25 % of the energy, respectively [19] (**Fig. 1, b**). This flow phenomenon has caused the MBT to be considered a two-stage partial impulse turbine, because the first stage can operate with a degree of reaction and the second stage operates with the pure impulse principle [11, 20].

Fig. 1. Crossflow turbine Michell-Banki:
a – isometric view of the MBT; *b* – side view of the MBT runner

In **Fig. 2**, an MBT is schematically represented, showing the fluid flow through the two stages described above and the corresponding velocity triangles in each stage. When the fluid passes through the nozzle, it acquires an absolute speed (v) and a relative speed with respect to the blades (w_1), which have an angle α_1 and β_1 with respect to the tangential speed, respectively. These angles tend to be constant across the azimuth position of the nozzle because the geometry of the rear-wall nozzle provides uniformity to the flow rate that crosses the blades in the first stage. Then, the fluid exits at an angle α_2 and β_2 from the first stage, which will directly affect the entry angles to the second stage. In this work, only the speed triangles will be analyzed in the first stage, since in this stage the greatest amount of energy is delivered and, in addition, it is the one that directs the fluid to the second stage.

Fig. 2. Schematic flow illustration of a MBT [10]

2. 2. MBT design

Dimensioning of the different components of the MBT begins by determining the fluid inlet velocity to the runner using (1) [18]:

$$v = c_v \sqrt{2gH}, \quad (1)$$

where v is the inlet velocity at the runner, c_v is the loss coefficient through the nozzle, g is the gravity acceleration (m/s^2) and H is the net head. At ideal conditions, c_v is considered 1 while experimentally, has been reported values for about 0.95 [19]. In **Fig. 3**, the kinematics of the fluid at the runner inlet are represented by means of the velocity triangle, where the angle of attack of the fluid is shown (α), for which different numerical and experimental studies recommend values between 12° and 22° [12, 17]. Then, because the tangential velocity of the fluid (v_t) is a function of the angle of attack, it can be expressed by (2) [21]:

$$v_t = v \cos(\alpha). \quad (2)$$

Subsequently, to determine the angle of the relative speed of the fluid at the runner inlet in the first stage (β_1), (3) was used, which improves the turbine performance [22]:

$$2 \tan(\alpha) = \tan(\beta_1). \quad (3)$$

A good turbine design requires that $\beta_1 \approx \beta_{1b}$, where β_{1b} is the blade angle with respect to the runner tangent shown in **Fig. 4**, this in order to avoid the separation of the flow [10]. Then, for the selection of the internal angle of the blades (β_2) in the first stage, different authors agree that the optimal value is 90° [10, 12, 18].

Fig. 3. Velocity triangle at the runner inlet [14]

Fig. 4. Blade geometry of a MBT [12]

Subsequently, the extern diameter of the rotor (D_{ext}) is determined using **Table 1**, depending on the relationship between flow rate (Q) and head (H).

Table 1
Runner diameter selection [23]

Q/\sqrt{H}	Diameter del rotor (mm)
0.02236–0.04743	200
0.04743–0.07906	300
0.07906–0.11068	400
0.11068–0.15812	500

To determine the internal diameter of the runner, in the literature it is recommended a ratio of internal diameter to external diameter equal to 0.68, using (4) [12]:

$$\frac{D_{int}}{D_{ext}} = 0.68. \quad (4)$$

Then, in the literature is determine that the radius and the blades curvature angle (δ and R_B) can be determined using (5) and (6), respectively [22]:

$$R_B = \frac{R_{ext}^2 - R_{int}^2}{2R_{ext} \cos(\beta_1)}, \quad (5)$$

$$\tan\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) = \frac{\cos(\beta_1)}{\sin(\beta_1) + \frac{D_{ext}}{D_{int}}}, \quad (6)$$

where R_{ext} and R_{int} are the external and internal radius of the runner respectively. Subsequently, the width of the rotor (W) is calculated using (7):

$$W = \frac{QN_b}{\pi D_{ext} v \sin(\alpha) Z_a}, \quad (7)$$

where N_b is the number of blades, which are taken from the study made by [13] and Z_a corresponds to the number of wet blades in the first stage, which depend directly on θ_s and N_b . Then, the rotation speed (ω) of the turbine is determined by (8), which is given by [10]:

$$\frac{\omega_{max} R_{ext}}{v} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{h_0^2}{R_{ext}^2 \theta_s^2} \right), \quad (8)$$

where θ_s is the nozzle output angle taken by the study carried out by [10] and h_0 is the height of the nozzle outlet. Having the turbine rotation speed, the applicability of the MBT is validated according to the site conditions (Q and H), the specific numbers of revolution N_q and N_s are used, which vary between 18–60 and 60–200, respectively [24]:

$$N_q = \omega \frac{Q^{1/2}}{H^{3/4}}, \quad (9)$$

$$N_s = \omega \frac{P^{1/2}}{H^{5/4}}, \quad (10)$$

where P is the brake power (CV) and ω is the runner speed [RPM]. Afterwards, a calculation of the nozzle dimensions is started using (11) and (12):

$$\frac{h_0}{R_{ext} \theta_s} = 0.37, \quad (11)$$

$$B = \frac{W}{1.5}, \quad (12)$$

where B is the width of the nozzle.

Finally, the nozzle rear-wall curve is calculated as shown in **Fig. 5**, using (13) [10], where θ will take values from 0 to θ_s :

$$R_{(\theta)} = R_1 + h_0 \left(1 - \frac{\theta}{\theta_s} \right). \quad (13)$$

Fig. 5. Schematic illustration nozzle rear-wall of a MBT

2. 3. Design methodology of the hydrodynamic blades of the MBT

The difference between the model with tubular blades and the runner with modified hydrodynamic profiles is only in the blade calculation. However, there are some values that don't change when designing with blades with hydrodynamic profile, such as the angle of attack of the fluid, the chord angle of the NACA profile (blade position) and the angle of the relative velocity of the fluid [18].

Based on the results obtained by [16, 17], a change of curvature process is performed in the hydrodynamic profile NACA 6509 (**Fig. 6, a**) according to the curvature of the standard (tubular) blades, using the circumference equation it's possible to set the following equations:

$$x_1 = \sqrt{N - (x - M)^2}, \quad (14)$$

$$y_1 = x_1 + y, \quad (15)$$

where x and y , are the coordinates from each point of the profile, x and y_1 , are the new profile coordinates with respect to the y axis. M defines the profile inclination with respect to the axis and N determines the profile radius of curvature, which was taken according to the curvature of the tubular blade.

Finally, due to the NACA profile presents areas with thin thicknesses to be machined, a thickness modification is made based on the tubular profile, due to this change in the thickness of the NACA 6509 profile, the last two digits of the profile are modified that correspond to the maximum thickness in percentage of the chord length, becoming a NACA 6512 profile.

In **Fig. 6, b**, the overlap between the modified NACA 6512 profile and the conventional profile is presented, in order to qualitatively estimate the similarity of curvature, chord length and thickness of both profiles, to verify the behavior of each of these only varying the shape.

In **Fig. 7**, the two runners designs taken for this study are presented.

Fig. 6. Modified hydrodynamic profile:
a – Profile with curvature; *b* – Overlap of the NACA 6512 and tubular profiles

Fig. 7. Runners used for this study:
a – Runner with tubular blades; *b* – Runner with modified hydrodynamic blades

2. 4. Numerical method

The process of simulation of the momentum and mass conservation equations was carried out using the ANSYS® CFX module. The properties of the two-phase fluid were established for water and air at 25 °C with a reference pressure of 1 atm, since the operating conditions of the turbine do not generate changes in the density of both fluids, and a surface tension coefficient of 73.5 dyna cm⁻¹ was configured. The simulation was performed in a transient state with an initial time step of 0.001 s for a total simulation time of 0.6 s, using the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, since this model has accuracy in predicting the operation of turbomachines with a lower computational cost. The simulation process was performed on a high-speed computer (cluster), which is composed of the Windows Server 2008 R2 operating system and has a processing capacity of 32 cores and 256 GB RAM.

The general boundary conditions associated with the control volume shown in **Fig. 8, a** correspond to the operating conditions under which the design was made, for this reason a pressure of 4.9 kPa is configured at the nozzle inlet and the rotating (runner) domain with a rotation speed of 140 RPM on the y axis, with a subsonic flow, a relative pressure of zero (0) Pa and finally, the output is configured as opening. Then, a volumetric fraction for both fluids (air-water) is configured with zero gradient and the turbine walls and rotor blades are configured with a non-slip condition.

For a better data transfer between the rotating domain (runner) and the stationary domains (nozzle and housing) two interfaces were established, due to this a new domain (ring) must be generated to be able to configure them. The first interface (**Fig. 8, b**) occurs between the nozzle, the ring and the housing. For this, a «fluid-fluid» type interface is implemented where the ring regions that limit with the other domains (nozzle and housing) are selected and the nozzle and housing regions, which border the ring, then a «general connection» interface model is implemented and because neither of the named domains rotates with respect to the other, there is no mix/change model framework. The second interface between the ring and the runner, where like the first interface is also configured as «fluid-fluid» and the limits of each model are selected (**Fig. 8, c**) but unlike the first interface, this one has a moving domain (runner), therefore, the mixing/changing model

frame is set as «Transient Runner Stator», due to the transient conditions of the fluid between the nozzle and the rotor.

Fig. 8. Boundary conditions:
a – General Boundary conditions; *b* – First interface; *c* – Second interface

The discretization of the fluid volumes of the MBT is done in the Meshing module, using an unstructured tetrahedral mesh with a prismatic layer near the wall regions. In **Fig. 9**, the efficiency based on the number of elements for the two (2) models studied is presented, for the MBT mesh independence study, five (5) different meshes were applied from 2.1 to 10.3 million elements and 3.8 to 13.9 million elements, for the model with standard profiles (tubular) and the model with modified NACA 6512 profiles, respectively. In numerical calculation, as the mesh size decreases, the results obtained in the CFX are more accurate but the computational cost is higher. In this way it was possible to determine that the error rate is approximately 1 % for mesh four (4) with respect to mesh five (5), so the four (4) is selected because it is possible to guarantee an almost the same result with a lower computational cost. Additionally, a time step independence is performed for the model with hydrodynamic profiles as shown in **Fig. 10**, it was determined that the error rate is approximately 1 % for the time step equal to 0.002 s with respect to the time step of 0.001 s, but the simulation time was much higher because it did not converge in the programmed iterations, therefore, a time step of 0.001 s is selected, guaranteeing a reliable simulation response. Due to the constant monitoring of the torque generated by the turbine as a function of time, it was possible to guarantee the stability of response both numerically by RMS less than 1E-4 and at the level of stationary flow condition by evidencing that the torque does not vary as a function of the rotation of the rotor, reaching stationary operating conditions [13].

In **Fig. 11**, a flow chart that summarizes the methodology that was implemented for the development of this study is presented.

Fig. 9. Mesh independence

Fig. 10. Timestep independence

Fig. 11. Flowchart of the numerical process

3. Results and discussion

In Table 2, the results of the MBT design are presented using equations 1–15, for the two models studied, for which only the blade profile is changed. Therefore, the design methodology is the same.

Table 2
Geometrical configuration of the MBT

Design parameters	Notation	Values	Units
Extern diameter	D_{ext}	200	mm
Internal diameter	D_{int}	136	mm
Blade output angle	β_{2b}	90	degrees
Blade input angle	β_{1b}	36	degrees
Number of blades	N_b	28	–
Runner width	W	153	mm
Nozzle width	B	102	mm
Nozzle height	h_0	65	mm
Nozzle output arc	θ_s	93	degrees

In Fig. 12, *a*, the efficiency as a function of the speed ratio for the MBT is presented for the model configured with tubular profile and with modified NACA 6512 profiles, for which five (5) simulations were carried out varying the RPM from 100 to 200, with steps of 20 obtaining an optimum number of 160 and 140 RPM with an efficiency of 83 % and 89 % for the model with tubular blades and the model with modified NACA 6509 profiles, respectively. From the results, this study showed similarities with the study presented in the Fig. 12, *b* [18]. First, the results for both studies had the maximum efficiency with a speed ratio close to 1.8. In addition, the maximum efficiencies for this study with the tubular profiles, had similar results with the experimental study conducted in [25], about 83 % both with standard profiles.

Fig. 12. Crossflow turbine speed ratio:
a – Efficiency of NACA 6512 and tubular; *b* – Efficiency obtained by [19]

In Fig. 13, the volumetric fraction contours in the turbine symmetry plane (*XY*) are presented for both models (tubular runner and runner with modified NACA 6512 profiles), in the model with tubular runner (Fig. 13, *a*), no flow separation is presented when passing the first and second stage, because with the new design of the nozzle it is possible to ensure a greater coincidence

between the angles of the relative fluid speed and the position of the blades ($\beta_1 \approx \beta_{1b}$), along the azimuthal position at the runner inlet [9]. In **Fig. 13, b**, it is observed that for the model with modified hydrodynamic blades, a flow detachment occurs in the first stage, thus generating turbulence in the cross flow, this may be due to the increase in the thickness of the blades at the fluid inlet and to the change of section that occurs in these profiles, characteristics that do not present the standard profiles (tubular), because they are completely symmetrical.

Fig. 13. Volumetric water fraction in the models studied:
a – MBT with standard runner; *b* – MBT with modified hydrodynamic profile

In **Fig. 14**, the pressure contours in the plane of symmetry of the MBT are presented for the two (2) models studied, where it can be seen that for the model with modified NACA 6512 blades (**Fig. 14, b**) lower pressures are obtained on the convex sides of the blades in the first stage with respect to the model with tubular blades (**Fig. 14, a**), due to the fact that they are mainly used in the aeronautical industry presenting high lift coefficients, increasing the reaction degree of the MBT in the first stage, which increases the power transmitted to the shaft.

Fig. 14. Pressure contours in the models studied:
a – MBT with standard runner; *b* – MBT with modified hydrodynamic profile

In **Fig. 15**, the water speed vectors in the nozzle and the turbine rotor are shown, where it can be seen that the speed differential between the convex and concave part, for each model are different, being the model with modified hydrodynamic profiles (**Fig. 15, b**) the one that presents the highest speed differential, which explains why there are higher vacuum pressures for it and therefore, the degree of reaction in the first stage increases.

Fig. 15. Velocity vectors for the models studied:
a – MBT with standard runner; *b* – MBT with modified hydrodynamic profile

Based on these results, the concept of reaction turbine using NACA type hydrodynamic profiles can be further used. Due to this, it can still be verified which modified NACA profiles will have a higher impact on the efficiency of the MBT.

In this work, the generation of cavitation created by the low pressures at the edges of the NACA profiles and the effect on the performance and structure of the turbine was not analyzed. Therefore, it will be an aspect of importance in further research. Additionally, is important to validate the behavior of the NACA profiles experimentally analyzing the cost-benefit of this modification.

4. Conclusions

This work will serve as a starting point for future research to study the behavior of modified hydrodynamic profiles. A design methodology is provided based on site conditions. Based on the results of the study, a MBT using blades with NACA 6512 profiles modified according to the curvature and chord length of the standard profiles (tubular) presents a better hydraulic performance compared to the model with tubular blades, with maximum efficiencies of 89 % and 83 %, respectively. There are two reasons for the increase in efficiency.

First, the hydrodynamic profile meets the fluid inlet and outlet angles due to the modification that was made. Second, in the first stage there is an increase in the fluid velocity on the convex side of the blades (**Fig. 15, b**), so the greater velocity differential in the blades creates a greater decrease in the pressures in the convex part of the modified NACA 6512 profiles compared to the standard profiles, so that the torque and energy transmitted increases.

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